

Establishing Research Priorities in a Palliative Care Institution through Systematic Strategic Planning

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 26 May 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Sreejini Jaya</p> <p>KEYWORDS: strategic planning, prioritization, palliative care, research priority.</p>	<p>Strategic planning is vital for maintaining an organization's long-term vitality and effectiveness. Given the numerous potential research areas in palliative care, it is crucial to identify research priorities in a palliative care setting. The study aims to identify and prioritize feasible research priorities in palliative care and gather potential implementation recommendations. We completed the study in three phases: an online survey to gather potential research questions and a prioritization process, where participants select a few critical areas based on their importance, followed by active interactions with a panel of experts to finalize the top three research areas. In Phase 1, participants chose patient care and management as the most relevant area, followed by outcome measures and quality improvement, and psychosocial aspects as the most appropriate areas for research. Patient care and management were the highest priority needs, followed by outcome measures and quality improvement in Phase 2. Phase 3 helped identify the most highly prioritized need based on expert consensus. Each phase of the study contributed to narrowing down the options through prioritization and consensus-building. Such studies will assist the department and organization develop primary research initiatives focused on the most critical and prioritized research areas.</p>

Introduction

Planning is one of the most important aspects of any organisation's administration. An organisation must assess its current state, determine its future goals and understand the path to success, achieved through careful planning. Strategic planning is a disciplined effort that shapes any organisation's actions and decisions, clarifying its purpose and direction. It acts as a roadmap, requiring an analysis of the operational environment to address critical challenges and issues.¹ Strategic planning is a forward-looking process designed to set priorities, allocate resources, strengthen operations and ensure the long-term strength of any organisation. It is a set of decision-making criteria and the decisions made and implemented by an organisation to definitively and permanently guide its activities and structure.² Strategic planning can also be defined as a rational-comprehensive approach to strategy formulation that involves a systematic process with specific steps such as external and internal assessments, goal setting, analysis, evaluation and action planning to ensure the organisation's long-term vitality and effectiveness.³ Therefore, strategic planning involves

concepts, procedures, tools and practices designed to help decision-makers and stakeholders focus on what is truly important for their organisations. It can also be applied by any organisation or part, for intra-organisational functions (like finance or human resources), purpose-driven inter-organisational networks or collaborations intended to carry out particular tasks like transportation, health, education or emergency services.³

Strategic planning is critical in healthcare organizations, where interdisciplinary teams work closely to ensure positive patient outcomes.⁴ An organization's mission statement provides a framework for all organizational operations and specifies the type of care and guiding principles for healthcare organizations. Generally the vision statement sets future goals of the organization, and strategic planning involves refining the mission statement into quantifiable objectives. The SOAR model (Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results) is an alternative to SWOT analysis. It focuses on future-oriented goals and requires participation from all organizational segments, making it suitable for healthcare organizations.⁴

Strategic planning is employed to pinpoint key research areas and guide the direction of future studies. The National Cancer Institute (NCI) Cohort Consortium, an international collaborative organization, undertook a formal strategic planning process to align its goals with its mission.⁵ This process was conducted in four phases: Phase 1, ideas generated through online surveys and in-person discussions to identify and prioritize key themes; Phase 2, which involved drafting the strategic plan; Phase 3, which finalized the plan; and Phase 4, which focused on implementing the plan. This process allowed the consortium to assess scientific priorities, foster a culture of evaluation and collaboration, improve research operations, engage new investigators, optimize resources and take advantage of cost-effective technologies.⁵ In another study, strategic planning involved three key steps: Strategy development, implementation and evaluation.⁶

Given the numerous potential research areas in palliative care, it is crucial to identify feasible and practical research priorities in a palliative care setting, setting the stage for future research directions. Decisions about research priorities in a palliative care setting seldom rely on key stakeholder's priorities. Therefore, a collaborative effort is necessary to pinpoint these viable research areas within the organization. As an organization, we adopted an innovative approach to incorporate the key stakeholders' voices in palliative care delivery. The Research and Innovation department conducted a research priority-setting exercise with the potential to impact the field of palliative care significantly. This proposed study identifies and outlines research priorities in a palliative care institution through systematic strategic planning.

Methods

This study involves strategic planning in palliative care to identify and prioritize research questions in three phases. It includes an online survey to gather potential research questions, a prioritization process where participants select a few critical areas based on their importance, and an expert consensus to identify the most highly prioritized need. The significant domains for identifying research questions were ‘Patient care and management’, ‘Psychosocial aspects’, ‘Organisational & operational research’, ‘Education & Training’, ‘Specific populations and conditions’, ‘Innovative approaches’, ‘Policy and ethics’ and ‘Outcome measures & Quality Improvement’.

Phase 1/Assessment Phase: We developed and circulated an online survey tool (Google form) to all the participants outlining the aim of the exercise. The participants were asked to assess the given research priority areas and also given the leeway to propose new research priority areas. This exercise was administered to the institution staff involved with direct patient care, department heads, facilitation teams, education and skill-building departments, management, and other associated advisors of the institution. Participants were

allowed to participate in the next phase, which involves rating/prioritising the research questions.

Phase 2/Prioritization Phase: This phase depicts a second level of prioritization from consented participants. The participants prioritized the new list of research areas through an exercise. New lists comprised 12 research priority areas highly rated in Phase-1 and those new research priority areas that emerged from Phase-1. Participants were requested to rank any six research priority areas per their preference. The participants can select only six research priority areas based on their preference under each priority group [Example: Psychosocial aspects as priority three only]. The ranking of the priorities is from 1 to 6, with '1' indicating the highest priority and '6' indicating the least priority. This exercise ensures that the higher the number of points for a research priority, the higher the chance of selecting that research priority.

Phase 3/Consensus Building: The third and final step of the strategic planning exercise was among the selected panel of experts. The panel of experts comprises committee members from the Research and Innovation department of the palliative care institution. The facilitator explained the whole process to each expert and defined what they would like to accomplish by conducting this strategic planning exercise. Updating was essential as it helps experts understand the problem statement before providing their opinion. Among the first three highly prioritized needs (five), the panel of experts will decide on three key research priority areas through active interactions. Then, the experts will decide on individual topic areas/research questions/gaps pertaining to each research area.

Results

The results of the study are organized in a phased manner.

Phase 1/Assessment Phase: Of the 86 people contacted, 39.5% responded to Phase 1 of the survey. The mean age of the participants is 40.91 years, ranging from 25 to 77 years. Almost equal proportions of males (47.1%) and females (52.9%) participated in the survey. The participants were from different sections: 50% were from the healthcare workforce, 23.5% belonged to the management level, and 11.8% were from supportive departments. 14.7% of respondents were from other departments, including the board of trustees, scientists, academics, and heads of departments. Participants chose patient care and management (67.6%) as the most relevant research area (see Figure 1). Outcome measures and quality improvement (61.8%) and psychosocial aspects (50%) were also selected as the most relevant areas to be researched: education and training and innovative approaches chosen by 44.1% of the participants in Phase 1. Organizational and operational research (35.3%), research involving specific populations and conditions (26.5%) and research on policy and ethics (20.6%) were also selected in Phase 1. 6.8% of the participants were unclear on which subjects the research should focus on.

Figure 1: Preliminary result of Assessment Phase

Participants have come up with other topics of interest that need to study, such as the role of community in healthcare, palliative care in healthcare, research related to patient’s families, patient and carer perspectives, met and unmet needs, communication, rehabilitation, sexuality, technology and improving the quality of life of patients through vocational rehabilitation, realist evaluation of current palliative care services and implementation research using person-centred approach, research on the implementation outcomes like patient reach out, community engagement, research specific to non-cancer illnesses and palliative care, focus on pain management and patient care and management with caregiver education. Around 94.1% of the participants agreed to participate in the following survey phases.

Phase 2/Prioritization Phase: Two of the 34 respondents in Phase 1 wished to discontinue the study. Among the people who responded and consented, 22 (68.75%) continued with Phase 2. Each participant identified six priority areas ranging from 1 to 6; '1' indicates the highest priority, and '6' indicates the least. Outcome measures and quality improvement were the highly prioritized needs (86.4%) and were also selected as the second-highest need in first priority and highest in second priority (see Figure 2). Patient care and management were the highest priority in the first category. Education and training (63.6%), patient care and management (59.1%), met and unmet health care needs, community engagement, non-cancer care and palliative care were also prioritized at 50%.

Figure 2: Result of the Prioritization phase

Patient care and management, outcome measures and quality improvement, education and training, community

engagement, non-cancer care, and palliative care were the only needs that fell in the first three highly prioritized

research areas (see Figure 3), showcasing their importance to be studied.

Figure 3: Figure showcasing the first three highly prioritized research areas (Phase 2)

Phase 3/Consensus Building: Experts believe prioritization of research areas in the Research and Innovation department is essential. Among the first three highly prioritized needs (five), the panel of experts decided on three key research priority areas through active interactions. Experts agreed on individual topic areas/ research questions/gaps pertaining to each research area. In this phase, the highest prioritized needs were Outcome measures and quality improvement, Community Engagement and Education & training. Apart from the three research priority areas, Patient care & management also showcased equal importance. Through expert consensus, those areas that need research in palliative care are caregiver burden, training (medical students and other health care professionals), psychological support, policy analysis, and economics evaluation-based studies.

DISCUSSION

In this study, the strategic planning process enabled the palliative care institution to generate and refine research priority areas, paving the way for future research priorities. Strategic planning is essential in Indian health services as it helps address unique challenges and opportunities within the health system.⁷ However, the healthcare environment is complex and dynamic, and the health sector is a complex, uncertain, and ever-changing environment.⁸ However, even the complex organizations, such as the public health system, have established adaptive, creative and capable ways of developing solutions to problems, and often, these are bottom-up approaches.⁸ Strategic planning in any healthcare organization involves creating objectives and setting goals for where the organization sees itself in the long term. Strategic healthcare planning helps us understand how an

organization should operate to create a feasible plan. To achieve this, each phase of our study contributed to narrowing the options through prioritization and consensus-building. Prioritization methodology has always been used in formulating a strategic plan, which deals with choices among different options and strategies. It will help achieve the higher needs identified by analysing and evaluating problems.⁹ Our study also focused on the core principles of prioritization and helped us to rank the priority. Such studies will assist the department and the organization in developing primary research initiatives focused on the most critical and prioritized research areas, hoping for further advancement. Studies have revealed that the pace at which forces in the environment change is one reason for engaging in strategic planning.⁶ This prioritization exercise was crucial for any strategic planning exercise and helped to focus research on prioritized research areas. Researchers can follow it up by assigning priorities within a set of strategic research needs.

CONCLUSION

This study's prioritization methodology for strategic planning envisages using specific attributes for which a graded scale of values was established for each research need, allowing a quantitative comparison among them. It is unique because the subjective component captured through a qualitative evaluation was quantified. Expert consensus and discussion in the study highlighted each research need. Further selection of participants helps select and characterize each research priority or need. As part of any department strengthening, it helps strengthen the volume of research and helps the department build skills in prioritized research areas. However, the study has potential limitations, as using a tiny

sample size may impact the study result. Most of the time, it is a subjective perception that may affect the final consensus built.

Acknowledgments

The author(s) would like to thank all of their participants, including staff involved with direct patient care, department heads, facilitation teams, education and skill-building departments, management, and other associated advisors of Pallium India.

Author's contributions

S.J. and A.S. contributed substantially to the work's concept and design; S.J. drafted and concluded the article, analysed data, revised the article critically and approved the version to be published. Both authors have read and approved the manuscript.

Funding statement

The author(s) received no financial support for this article's research, authorship, and/or publication.

Data availability statement

The datasets generated and analysed during the study are not publicly available because of the institution's privacy.

Declarations

Ethical approval and informed consent statements

This study was deemed exempt from review (TIPS/IEC-3/2024Exp) by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Trivandrum Institute of Palliative Sciences since the study involved prioritization of research needs based on one's preference without any linked identifiers, and disclosure would not harm the interests of the observed person. This study followed an online survey mode, with proper consent taken from the participants before the start of the survey.

Consent for publication

The manuscript does not contain any individual person's data.

Conflicting interest

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning this article's research, authorship, and/or publication.

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